

which was recrystallised from petroleum ether—benzene, (60%), m.p. 182° (Found: C, 81.41; H, 5.40; N, 3.97. $C_{24}H_{19}NO_2$ requires: C, 81.58; H, 5.38; N, 3.96%).

3-Methyl-5-phenyl-3',4'-dihydro-spiro[2-isoxazoline-4,2'-(1'H)-naphthalen-1-one](3b): 2-Benzal-1-tetralone (0.01 mol), nitroethane (0.01 ml) and phenyl isocyanate (0.02 mol) were taken in dry benzene. The solution was cooled in an ice-water bath and stirred while few drops of triethylamine in benzene were added dropwise during 10 min. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h while stirring. Separated diphenyl urea was removed by filtration. The filtrate was washed with water repeatedly and dried. The product was recrystallised from benzene, (40%), m.p. 196° (Found: C, 78.29; H, 5.81; N, 4.78. $C_{19}H_{17}NO_2$ requires: C, 78.35; H, 5.84; N, 4.81%).

Antibacterial activity: Antibacterial activity was assayed by employing Vincent and Vincent⁷ agar-disc method. All the bacteria employed, both the gram-positive (*Bacillus purnilis*, *Bacillus polymixa* and *Streptococcus albus*) and gram-negative (*Acetobacter acerogenes*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Pseudomonas ovalis*) were found to be moderately sensitive to the compounds under investigation.

Antifungal activity: The fungicidal activity was studied by glass slide-humid chamber technique⁸ against four phytopathogenic fungi (*Fusarium oxysporum* Schl., *Curvularia lunata* (Walker) Boed., *Drechslera rostrata* and *Alternaria alternata*). The compounds exhibited strong fungicidal activity against all the four organisms and caused total inhibition at 200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration. The log ED_{50} values for *F. oxysporum*, *C. lunata*, *D. rostrata* and *A. alternata* were 2.1, 2.2, 2.06 and 2.08, respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. E. V. Sundaram, for facilities, and to Dr. K. Nagarajan, Director, Searle R & D Centre, Thane, for helpful discussion.

References

1. T. SUZUKI, M. ITAYA, G. MINAMI, B. MIYASACA, Y. TERUTANI and H. MIKI, *Chem. Abstr.*, **73**, 14835.
2. C. J. RAO, Ph.D. Thesis, Kakatiya University, 1979.
3. C. J. RAO, K. M. REDDY and A. K. MURTHY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, **1981**, **20**, 282.
4. E. RAJANARENDAR and A. K. MURTHY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, **1981**, **20**, 608.
5. C. Y. SHIUE, R. G. LAWLER and L. B. OLAPP, *J. Org. Chem.*, **1976**, **41**, 2211.
6. M. OHASHI, H. KAMACHI, H. KAKISAWA, A. TATEMATSU, H. YOSHIZUMI and H. NAKATA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, **1968**, 379.
7. J. C. VINCENT and H. B. VINCENT, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, **1944**, **55**, 162.
8. ANON, *Phytopathology*, **1947**, **37**, 3540.

3,3'-Di-O-methylellagic-acid-4-O- β -D-galactopyranosyl-(1 $\rightarrow$ 4)- β -D-glucopyranoside from Stem Bark of *Diospyros discolor* Willd.

SANTOSH K. SRIVASTAVA* and SANDHYA PITRE

Department of Chemistry, University of Saugar, Saugar-470 003

Manuscript received 7 October 1985, revised 19 May 1986, accepted 13 November 1986

THE plant *Diospyros discolor* (syn. *D. mabola*) is a medicinal plant, employed in the indigenous system of medicine^{1,2}. The previous study on the stem bark of *D. discolor* disclosed the presence of a new anthraquinone glycoside³ and a tannin⁴. Our further examination on the stem bark of this plant has now revealed the presence of a new glycoside 3,3'-di-O-methylellagic-acid-4-O- β -D-galactopyranosyl-(1 $\rightarrow$ 4)- β -D-glucopyranoside (1), characterised by spectral and chemical analyses.

The glycoside (1), m.p. 220–22° d, gave a yellow colour with alkali, a dark bluish green precipitate with FeCl_3 ⁵, and positive Greissmeyer's reaction⁶, suggesting that it to be an ellagic acid derivative⁵. Its ir (KBr) spectral bands at 3 440–3 410 (br, OH), 1 730 and 1 720 (lactone), 2 870 and 1 175 (methoxyl), 1 590, 1 560 and 1 470 (aromatic) and 820 cm^{-1} (glycoside), and uv (EtOH) characteristic bands at 249, 355 (sh) and 370 nm substantiated this assumption^{7–10}.

Acid hydrolysis of the glycoside gave an aglycone (2) and a mixture of sugars identified as D-galactose and D-glucose by direct comparison with authentic samples (co-pc); 2, m.p. 273–74°, $C_{16}H_{10}O_8$, λ_{max} (EtOH) 248, 359 (sh) and 372 nm analysed for two methoxyl groups (Zeisel's). Its uv spectra exhibited a bathochromic shift of 33 nm in presence of sodium ethylate but no bathochromic shift was discernible with sodium acetate indicating that the aglycone is 3,3'-di-O-methylellagic acid (2), which was confirmed by direct comparison (m.m.p. and co-tlc)⁷.

The glycoside on methylation with diazomethane and subsequent acid hydrolysis yielded 3,3',4'-tri-O-methylellagic acid, m.p. 287–88° (m.m.p. and co-tlc)⁴ which gave a monoacetate, m.p. 260–62° (m.m.p. and co-tlc)⁴. This observation confirmed that both the sugar units are linked at position-4 of the aglycone in the form of a disaccharide. The partial acid hydrolysis of the glycoside yielded D-galactose (co-pc) and 3,3'-di-O-methylellagic-acid-4-O-glucoside, m.p. 213–15°⁸. This is borne out by the fact that D-Galactose was thus proved to be the terminal sugar in 1.

The structure was finally established by permethylation (Hakomori's method)^{11,12} of the glycoside followed by acid hydrolysis which gave 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-galactose, 2,3,6-tri-O-methyl-D-glucose (R_G values and co-pc)^{13,14} and 3,3',4'-tri-O-methylellagic acid (m.m.p. and co-tlc). This confirmed the 1 $\rightarrow$ 4 inter-sugar linkage. The periodate

oxidation of glycoside which liberated one mole of HCO_2H with consumption of three moles of sodium metaperiodate supported the pyranose form of both the sugars. The almond enzymatic hydrolysis of the glycoside afforded **2** (m.m.p. and co-tlc), D-galactose and D-glucose (co-pc), confirming the β -linkage in both the sugars and the aglycone. This led to the formulation of new glycoside as 3,3'-di-O-methylellagic--acid-4-O- β -D-galactopyranosyl-(1 $\rightarrow$ 4)- β -D-glucopyranoside. The 60 MHz $^1\text{Hnmr}$ spectra (CDCl_3) of the acetylated glycoside also supported the formulation (**1**) for glycoside, δ 4.90 (1H, d, J 7Hz, H-1''), 4.70 (1H, d, J 7Hz, H-1''), 4.00 (3H, s, 1 $\times$ OMe), 3.90 (3H, s, 1 $\times$ OMe), 7.20 (2H, s, H-5 and 5'), 2.0 (3H, s, 1 $\times$ OAc), 2.06 (6H, s, 2''-OAc and (3''-OAc), 2.08 (3H, s, 6''-OAc), 2.04 (6H, s, 2''-OAc and 3''-OAc), 2.02 (3H, s, 4''-OAc), 2.10 (3H, s, 6''-OAc) and 3.50–3.80 (12H, m, sugar-protons).

1; R = galactosyl-(1 $\rightarrow$ 4)-glucoside
2; R = H

Experimental

Extraction: The air-dried and powdered stem bark (3 kg) of *D. discolor* procured from the United Chemical and Allied Product, Calcutta, was exhaustively extracted with rectified spirit under reflux for 30 days. The total spirit extract (40 dm³) was concentrated (300 ml) and poured into distilled water (1 dm³). The water-soluble fraction was concentrated to a syrupy mass and successively extracted with petroleum ether, C_6H_6 , CHCl_3 , EtOAc, Me_2CO and MeOH. The MeOH extract was passed through a column of silica gel and eluted from Me_2CO —MeOH (1 : 1). The eluate was concentrated and the product on crystallisation from MeOH—Et₂O mixture afforded brown coloured crystals of **1** (1.3 g) (Found; C, 51.39; H, 4.60. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_{18}$ calcd for: C, 51.39; H, 4.58%). Acetylation of **1** with Ac_2O /Py gave an acetate, m.p. 180–82° (Found; C, 53.29; H, 4.60. $\text{C}_{44}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_{20}$ calcd. for: C, 53.33; H, 4.64%).

Acid hydrolysis of the glycoside: The glycoside (800 mg) was refluxed with aqueous H_2SO_4 (7%, 40 ml) for 3 h, cooled and extracted with ether. The ether extract was evaporated and the residue crystallised (MeOH—Et₂O) to yield **2** as pale yellow crystals (lit. m.p. 274°) (Found: C, 58.12; H, 3.02; OMe, 18.75. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_8$ calcd. for: C, 58.18, H, 3.03; OMe, 18.78%). The aqueous layer after neutralisation (BaCO_3) was shown to be a mixture of D-galactose and D-glucose (co-pc).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, and Defence Laboratory, Gwalior, for the spectral and analytical data, and to Ms. A. Jain, Chemistry Department of this University for the authentic samples.

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1950, p. 163.
2. K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, "Indian Medicinal Plants", L. M. Basu, Allahabad, 1935, Vol. 1, p. 542.
3. S. K. SRIVASTAVA and S. PITRE, *Curr. Sci.*, 1985, **54**, 998.
4. A. JAIN and S. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1984, **53**, 1233.
5. B. P. MOORE, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1964, **17**, 901.
6. GREISSMEYER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1871, **51**, 160.
7. S. MALHOTRA and K. MISHRA, *Phytochemistry*, 1981, **20**, 2043.
8. L. R. ROW and G. S. R. S. RAO, *Tetrahedron*, 1962, **18**, 357.
9. T. R. SRSHADRI and K. VASISHTA, *Phytochemistry*, 1965, **4**, 312.
10. T. R. SRSHADRI and K. VASISHTA, *Phytochemistry*, 1965, **4**, 989.
11. L. JURD, K. J. PALMER, F. STILT and J. N. SHOOLERY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 4620.
12. S. HAKOMORI, *J. Biochem. Tokyo*, 1964, **55**, 205.
13. O. MIKES, "Chromatographic Method", Van Nostrand, London, 1967, p. 77.
14. F. LEDERER, "Chromatography", Elsevier, New York, 1967, p. 251.

Microdetermination of Phosphate with 2-Carboxy-2'-hydroxy-3',5'-dimethylazobenzene-4-sulphonic Acid

S. B. GHOLSE* and B. K. DESHMUKH

Laxminarayan Institute of Technology, Nagpur University,
Nagpur-440 010

Manuscript received 18 October 1982, revised 8 October 1986,
accepted 13 November 1986

2-CARBOXY-2'-hydroxy-3',5'-dimethylazobenzene-4-sulphonic acid (CHDMAS, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}$) has been described as a reagent for the spectrophotometric studies of Pd^{II} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} ^{1,2}, Fe^{III} and Al^{III} ³. Bokare *et al.*⁴ determined the stepwise stability constant of CHDMAS- Fe^{III} complex using a potentiometric technique. The reagent has also been employed for the determination of fluoride in water⁵. The decrease of absorbance of the Mg^{II} -CHDMAS complex on addition of phosphate at the λ_{max} has been found to be quantitative, and a method has been evolved for the determination of phosphate in trace quantities.

Experimental

Mg^{II} and phosphate solutions were prepared by dissolving magnesium sulphate (A.R.) and potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate (A.R.), respectively,